

Empirical Research On Aesthetic Education In Art Colleges And Universities: Survey And Data Analysis On The Status Quo Of College Students' Ecological Aesthetic Literacy

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 24, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Aesthetic Education , Art Colleges</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6481503</p>	<p><i>At present, in the process of cultivating art talents, it has been increasingly revealed that the lack of ecological reflection and the lack of ecological design thinking in design. The ecological aesthetic model based on the premise of symbiosis with nature will surely drive the evolution of the design field and design concept. This study investigates and analyzes the current situation of ecological aesthetic literacy of college students in Shanxi, China. A total of 1,100 questionnaires were distributed and 997 valid questionnaires were returned. The purpose is to provide a basis for the curriculum design strategy of artistic ecological aesthetic education. The research results show that innovation literacy has a significant impact on aesthetic literacy; ecological literacy also has a significant impact on aesthetic literacy; the improvement of ecological values also has a significant impact on aesthetic ability. Aesthetic literacy is inextricably linked with innovation literacy and ecological literacy, and the three promote and build on each other. College students have a strong sense of aesthetics, and there are obvious differences in many dimensions, such as men and women, parents' educational background, family income, art training, and ecological aesthetics courses. Focusing the broad aesthetic education on the aesthetic education curriculum design of art design majors from the perspective of ecological aesthetic education is undoubtedly a practical path for in-depth research on the construction of aesthetic education in art colleges.</i></p>

Introduction

Ecological aesthetic literacy. The 2018 National Education Conference pointed out that "to comprehensively strengthen and improve school aesthetic education, Adhere to educating people with beauty and culture, and improve students' aesthetic and humanistic quality. "Aesthetic quality is humanistic quality. Some scholars have pointed out that aesthetic quality is mainly based on aesthetic common sense, aesthetic concept and aesthetic behavior. The aesthetic psychology of indicators (Zhao Lingli and Wang Hong, 2010), usually regards aesthetic quality as a kind of psychological ability of human beings, power to understand. The main purpose of ecological aesthetic education with art education as the main way is to create a relationship between man and nature,

A broad ecological harmonious atmosphere and harmonious aesthetic relationship between people and society, between people and themselves, in order to improve people's ecological aesthetic quality. Ecological aesthetic education is the deepening and development of ordinary aesthetic education, and its important task. It is to cultivate and improve students' ecological aesthetic quality. Aesthetic literacy refers to the aesthetic experience and aesthetic feeling that a person possesses. It is the sum of various factors such as interest, aesthetic ability, and aesthetic ideal. Aesthetic literacy is both reflected in the acceptance and appreciation of beauty. The ability to reward is transformed into the ability to identify aesthetic culture and the ability to create aesthetic culture.

Aesthetic awareness refers to "the thoughts, cognitions, emotions and intentions that form, develop and dominate people's aesthetic activities in aesthetic activities. The general name of Zhi" (Huang Xiting, Yang Zhiliang and Lin Chongde, 2003), Ecological aesthetic awareness refers to whether an individual can It is enough to perceive the existence of beauty in an ecological way, to know the value and standard of beauty, and personal aesthetic ideals. It is in a basic position in the framework of college students' aesthetic quality; and the ecological aesthetic common sense is the college students' understanding of the ecological system. The cognition of beauty, aesthetics and aesthetic education included in cognition; ecological aesthetic behavior refers to the types of aesthetic activities of college students and fields, including natural beauty, social beauty, artistic beauty and scientific beauty. Ecological aesthetic literacy refers to "knowing Appreciate and maintain the beauty of ecology" (Ma Yan, 2015), can treat nature with an aesthetic attitude, care for life and

protect the environment (Li Liangjin and Li Zhide, 2014), have the ability to create ecological beauty, so as to form a suitable.

A beautiful ecological environment in which species and other life live, this is a higher level of ecological literacy, college students as special groups with advanced thinking and strong learning ability who are receiving higher education should strive to improve their own. Ecological aesthetic literacy, get rid of the influence of the wrong ecological view of "anthropocentrism", from the "no environment in the heart." Selfish ecological concept, moving towards a friendly ecological concept of "environment everywhere", for the protection and governance of the ecological environment, for the contribution of the construction of my country's ecological civilization. To sum up, we start from aesthetic literacy, ecological outlook and innovation. Three aspects of ability are used to measure the ecological aesthetic literacy of college students.

I. Research framework

The core variable of this study is the aesthetic quality of art college students. In order to understand the main factors affecting the aesthetic literacy of art college students, a sample survey was conducted to compare the aesthetic literacy levels of college students in different majors. The main factors affecting the level of aesthetic literacy of college students can be divided into three aspects: genetic factors, family factors and educational factors. At the same time, aesthetic literacy is inextricably linked with innovation literacy and ecological literacy, and the three promote and build on each other. The relationship between the variables is shown in Figure 3-1:

Figure 3-1 Research Architecture Diagram

3.2 Statistical assumptions

According to the research purpose and research framework, the statistical hypotheses are put forward as follows:

Assuming H1, there are significant differences in innovation literacy, ecological literacy and aesthetic literacy due to genetic factors, namely gender.

- Assuming H1a, there is a significant difference in innovation literacy scores between boys and girls.
- Assuming H1b, there is a significant difference in aesthetic literacy scores between boys and girls.
- Assuming H1c, there is a significant difference in the ecological literacy scores between boys and girls.

Hypothesis H2, college students with different family conditions have significant differences in innovation literacy, ecological literacy and aesthetic literacy.

Hypothesis H2a,

- ① Different parents' occupations have significant differences in the scores of college students' innovation literacy.
- ② There are significant differences in the scores of college students' innovation literacy with different parents' educational level.
- ③ There are significant differences in the scores of innovation literacy of college students depending on the location of their families.
- ④ There are significant differences in the scores of college students' innovation literacy with different family economic levels.

Hypothesis H2b,

- ① Different parents' occupations have significant differences in the scores of college students' aesthetic literacy.
- ② There are significant differences in the scores of college students' aesthetic literacy with different parents' educational level.
- ③ There are significant differences in the aesthetic literacy scores of college students depending on the location of their families.
- ④ There are significant differences in the scores of college students' aesthetic literacy with different family economic levels.

Assuming H2c,

- ① different parents' occupations have significant differences in the ecological literacy scores of college students.
- ② There are significant differences in the ecological literacy scores of college students with different parents' educational level.
- ③ There are significant differences in the ecological literacy scores of college students according to different family locations.
- ④ There are significant differences in the ecological literacy scores of college students with different family economic levels.

Assuming H3, there are significant differences in innovation literacy, ecological literacy, and aesthetic literacy of college students with different educational conditions, especially aesthetic education.

Hypothesis H3a,

- ① Whether they have received art training or not, there are significant differences in the innovation literacy scores of college students who have received different art training.
- ② The innovation literacy scores of art college students are significantly different from those of other types of college students.
- ③ There is a significant difference in the innovation literacy scores of art majors and other majors.
- ④ The innovation literacy scores of college students who have studied ecological aesthetics courses are significantly different from those who have not studied related courses.

Hypothesis H3b,

- ① Whether they have received art training or not, there are significant differences in the aesthetic literacy scores of college students who have received different art training.
- ② The aesthetic literacy scores of art college students are significantly different from those of other types of college students.
- ③ There is a significant difference in aesthetic literacy scores between art majors and other majors.
- ④ The aesthetic literacy scores of college students who have studied ecological aesthetics courses are significantly different from those who have not studied related courses.

Hypothesis H3c,

- ① Whether they have received art training or not, there are significant differences in the ecological literacy scores of college students who have received different art training.
- ② The scores of ecological literacy of college students in art colleges are significantly different from those of college students in other types of colleges.
- ③ There is a significant difference in ecological literacy scores between art majors and other majors.
- ④ The ecological literacy scores of college students who have studied ecological aesthetics courses are significantly different from those who have not studied related courses.

Assuming H4, the scores of innovation literacy, aesthetic literacy, and ecological literacy are related in pairs.

3.3 Current Situation of Ecological Views of College Students

To measure the ecological outlook of college students, this research adopts the values scale compiled by Xu Qianyi (2008) (consisting of three subscales, namely altruistic values, altruistic values and ecological values)

and the Beijing Forestry University. The Chinese version of the New Ecological Paradigm (New Ecological Paradigm) revised by the Department of Psychology.

(1) The characteristics of college students' ecological values. The value scale compiled by Xu Qianyi (2008) used in this study has a total of 12 items, of which 1 to 4 are the measurement of altruistic values, 5 to 8 are the measurement of altruistic values, and 9 to 12 are the ecological values. Measurement. Each question adopts the Likert 5-point scoring method, and the score range of each value is 5-20 points. The higher the score, the more emphasis on the value. In order to facilitate understanding and comparison, this study converts the scores of each value into a percentage system. The results of frequency distribution analysis show that the average scores of sample college students' altruistic values, altruistic values and ecological values are 76.32 points for self-interest, 87.47 points for altruistic values, and 90.63 points for ecological values. Ecological values of college students scored the highest among the three values. In terms of score distribution, the score range of altruistic values is mainly concentrated in 60, 80 and 100 points, accounting for 59.1% of all samples; the score range of altruistic values is mainly concentrated in 80 and 100 points, accounting for 58.4% of all samples; ecological Value scores are also concentrated on 80 and 100 points, accounting for 84.1% of the total sample. By calculating the difference between ecological values and altruistic values, it can be seen that only 1.8% of the sample has a score of altruistic values higher than that of ecological values. value scores, and 31.9% of students scored the same. The specific data distribution is shown in Figure 3-2. In general, college students' recognition of the importance of ecological value is higher than that of profit.

Figure 3-2 Distribution of the difference between ecological values and self-interested values

College students of different genders have significant differences in ecological values. The average score of ecological values for boys in the sample is 87.89 points, and the average score of ecological values for women is 91.69 points. The independent sample T test was used to test the mean value of college students' ecological value scores. The results showed that the significance Sig value of the Levine variance equality test was 0.000, less than 0.05, and the overall variance was not equal. The mean equivalence T-test significance Sig value was 0.001, indicating a significant difference in the means of ecological values between males and females. The 95% confidence interval of the difference is -6.135~-1.479. The data are shown in Table 3-1.

独立样本检验										
莱文方差等同性检验				平均值等同性 t 检验						
		F	显著性	t	自由度	显著性 (双尾)	平均值差值	标准误差差值	差值 95% 置信区间	
									下限	上限
生态价值观	假定等方差	.750	.387	.329	995	.742	.377	1.145	-1.870	2.623
	不假定等方差			.347	373.422	.729	.377	1.086	-1.759	2.513

Table 3-1 Comparison of ecological value scores of different genders

The cross-tabular chi-square test was performed on the selection and gender of each item of ecological values, and the same result was obtained. An independent sample T test was conducted on the difference between the scores of ecological values and interest values and gender, and the results showed that there were significant differences in the scores of ecological values and interest values between different genders, and the score difference of female college students was significantly higher than that of male colleges. Poor score.

Using variance analysis to compare the ecological value scores of college students in different types of schools, the variance test has a significant Sig value of 0.051, the mean square between each group is 193.561, and the mean square within the group is 222.417, with a significant Sig value of 193.561. is 0.500, and there is no significant difference in the ecological values scores of college students in different types of schools. The analysis of variance also shows that there is no significant difference in the ecological value scores of college students from cities, towns, and rural areas; there is also no significant difference in the ecological value scores of college students with different occupations, educational backgrounds, and consumption levels of parents.

Using the independent sample T test to compare the ecological value scores of art majors and non-art majors, the significance Sig value is 0.661, indicating that art majors and non-art majors There were no significant differences in the students' scores for ecological values. This scale is measured in three dimensions, and ecological values only account for one-third, so the data on ecological values are not statistically significant.

(2) Statistical analysis of the new ecological paradigm scale

The New Ecological Paradigm Scale has a total of 15 items, of which 5 are negative dimensions, all of which are scored on a 5-point Likert scale. ~75 points, the higher the score, the more concerned about the environment and ecology. In order to facilitate understanding and comparison, this study converts all scores into a percentile scale, with a score ranging from 0 to 100 points. 50 points is the middle value, and more than 50 points represents a positive ecological attitude.

The data statistics show that the average score of the sample ecology is 59.19 points, the standard deviation is 13.13 points, and the overall score level is above the middle, indicating that there is still room for improvement. In terms of score distribution, the proportion of scores below 50 points (including 50 points) is 33.5%, and the proportion of more than 60 points (including 60 points) reaches 50.7%.

The mean ecological score of female college students is significantly higher than that of male college students. The mean ecological scores of female college students and male college students were compared by independent samples T-test, and it was found that the mean ecological score of female college students was significantly higher than the mean ecological score of male college students. The average ecological score of female college students was 60.70, and the average ecological score of male college students was 55.30. The significance Sig value of Levin's variance equality test is 0.077, the variance is linear, and the corresponding mean value equality T test significance Sig value is 0.000. It can be seen that the mean ecological scores of female college students and male college students are Significant differences. Judging from the distribution of scores, the proportion of female college students with a score below 50 (including 50 points) is only 28.0%, and the proportion of male college students is 47.7%; The proportion of students is 29.1%, and the proportion of male college students is 18.3%. See Figure 3-3. This is directly related to women's innate charity for the weak, their concern for ecology, and their own biological structure of motherly love.

Figure 3-3 Distribution of ecological scores for boys and girls

- There are significant differences in the mean ecological scores of college students in different types of schools and different majors.

Comparing the mean ecological scores of college students in different types of schools, it is found that the average ecological score of college students from normal schools is 60.92, followed by students from art schools at 59.14, and college students from science and engineering universities. The lowest score was 55.44. One-way ANOVA analysis shows that the variance test has a significant Sig value of 0.436, and the variance is linear. The mean square between groups is 1263.103, the mean square within the group is 169.148, and the significant Sig value is 0.000, indicating that different schools and universities There were significant differences between the ecological score means. LSD multiple comparisons show that there is no significant difference between the undergraduates of art colleges and normal colleges, and the significant Sig value is 0.076; there are significant differences between students; there is no significant difference between undergraduates in comprehensive and polytechnic colleges. Since there are significant differences in the mean ecological scores of college students of different genders, and the gender composition ratios in each type of school sample are different, gender may affect the difference between school types, so the comparison was performed again after controlling for the gender variable. The results of variance analysis showed that there were still significant differences between the mean ecological scores of college students in each institution.

One-way ANOVA analysis was performed on the mean values of ecological scores of students in different major categories. The significance Sig value of variance test was 0.774, and the variance was linear. The significant Sig value is 0.000, and there are significant differences in the mean ecological scores of college students of various majors. The LSD multiple comparison results show that the significance values between the mean values of college students' ecological scores in each major category are all less than 0.05, and there are significant differences between them. See Table 3-2 for specific data.

If the influence of gender is excluded, and the differences in the mean ecological scores of boys in different major categories and the mean ecological scores of girls in different major categories are examined separately, it can be seen that there is no significant difference between liberal arts boys and art boys. There are significant differences between the liberal arts, arts and science boys. The average ecological score of the science boys is significantly lower than that of the liberal arts and arts boys; the situation among the girls is different from that of the boys, and the arts girls There was no significant difference between the mean ecological scores of the students of biology and science, and there was a significant difference between the mean of ecological scores of the students of arts and arts and science.

多重比较

因变量: 生态得分百分制

LSD	(I) 专业类别	(J) 专业类别	平均值差值 (I-J)	标准误差	显著性	95% 置信区间	
						下限	上限
	文科类	理科类	6.60645 [*]	1.31171	.000	4.0324	9.1805
		艺术类	3.37350 [*]	.95630	.000	1.4969	5.2501
	理科类	文科类	-6.60645 [*]	1.31171	.000	-9.1805	-4.0324
		艺术类	-3.23296 [*]	1.18040	.006	-5.5493	-.9166
	艺术类	文科类	-3.37350 [*]	.95630	.000	-5.2501	-1.4969
		理科类	3.23296 [*]	1.18040	.006	.9166	5.5493

Table 3-2 Comparison of ecological scores of students in different major categories

- There are significant differences in the mean ecological scores of college students with different family backgrounds

In the study, we divided the home locations of college students into four categories: large cities, small cities, towns and villages. The results of the one-way ANOVA analysis show that the variance test significance value is 0.459, the mean square between the ANOVA groups is 558.769, the mean square within the group is 171.276, and the significance is 0.021, indicating that there are significant differences in the mean ecological score of college students in different family locations. . Combined with LSD multiple comparisons, it can be seen that the average ecological score of college students whose families are located in small and medium cities is the highest, which is significantly different from that of college students whose families are located in large cities and those whose families are located in rural areas. The average score of college students whose family is located in a big city is the lowest, which is not significantly different from the average score of college students whose family is located in a rural area, and is significantly different from the average score of college students whose family is located in a small city.

There are also significant differences in the mean ecological scores of corresponding college students depending on the occupation of the parents. From the perspective of categories, we divide the family occupation into state-owned units, private units, family self-employment and other four categories. State-owned units include state administrative organs, state-owned enterprises, institutions and other units and departments whose wages are paid by the state finance; private units include private enterprises, foreign enterprises, individual industrial and commercial households, etc.; belong to other categories. There is a strong correlation between college students' parent's parent's work unit, and the cross-tabular chi-square test results have a Pilsson chi-square asymptotic significance value of 0.000, a Phi value of 0.960, and a Clem's V value of 0.554. The average ecological score corresponding to the occupation of the parent is the private unit. The single-factor ANOVA analysis results show that the ecological mean score of the college student whose parent occupation is a private unit is significantly higher than that of the college students whose parent occupation is other. Differences; The mean ecological score of college students whose pro-occupation is a private unit is significantly different from that of college students whose pro-occupation is other and state-owned units. Private enterprises are more susceptible to environmental impacts, and thus they are also more concerned about social ecology.

The monthly consumption level of college students reflects the economic level of their families. ANOVA analysis shows that the average ecological score of college students whose monthly consumption level is between 1001 and 2000 yuan is the highest, and the average score of college students with other consumption levels is the highest. There were significant differences, and there were no significant differences among college students at other levels of consumption. The cross-tab chi-square test shows that there is a significant correlation between the location of the family and the consumption level. The proportion of college students whose consumption level is between 1,001 and 2,000 yuan is the highest in small and medium cities, reaching 72.7%. The ratio is low. Differences in household location also reflect differences in economic level.

3.4 Current Situation of College Students' Innovation

For the measurement of innovation of college students, this research simplified and revised on the basis of the "Quality Scale of Innovative Talents" (2007) designed by Yin Zhiyuan, and formed a simplified scale of 9 items, involving innovative consciousness, innovative thinking and Three dimensions of innovation capability. Each item is scored on a 5-point Likert scale, and the innovation score ranges from 9 to 45 points. The higher the score, the higher the innovation. In order to facilitate understanding and comparison, this study converts the total score of innovation into a percentile system, with a score range of 0 to 100.

The innovation scores of all samples were counted, with an average score of 70.07, a median of 72.22, and a mode of 75. The overall innovation score is above average. From the distribution of each score, the score below 20 points accounted for 1%, the score from 21 to 40 accounted for 2.3%, the score from 41 to 60 accounted for 23.1%, the score from 61 to 80 accounted for 50.3, and the score above 80 accounted for 23.3%. Compared with 23.3%, it is basically normal distribution. See Figure 3-4 for details.

Figure 3-4 Distribution of innovation scores

By testing the sample mean, the mean innovation score of boys is 70.28, and the mean innovation score of girls is 69.99. The independent sample T-test variance is not equal, and the corresponding mean-equivalent T-test significance value is 0.814, and there was no significant difference in mean innovation scores between boys and girls. Investigate the relationship between grade, school type, major category, home location, parent occupation and other college students' personal family background variables and innovation scores, and the sample mean shows certain differences: Innovation scores of freshmen The mean is the highest among the four grades, the mean innovation score of students in science and engineering schools is the highest among all types of schools, the mean innovation score of art majors is higher than that of general and science and engineering students, and students whose families are located in large cities The mean innovation score of students is higher than that of college students in small cities, towns and villages. However, these differences were not statistically significant when tested by independent sample t-test and ANOVA analysis.

- Family situation and innovation

Parents with different educational levels have significant differences in the mean innovation scores of their children. One-way ANOVA analysis was used to compare the mean innovation scores of college students with different parental education levels. The significance value of variance test was 0.003, less than 0.05, and the variance was not equal, so the mean equality was carried out. Robust test, the Milch significance value is 0.029, indicating that there is a significant difference between the mean values of children's innovation scores with different parents' educational backgrounds. The results of multiple comparisons by Tammney show that the average innovation score of college students whose parental education level is high school/secondary school is the highest, and there is a significant difference between those with junior high school education and below. There were no significant differences between the other categories. The relationship between parental education and mean innovation score is the same. This is related to the fact that the higher the parent's education level, the higher the level of self-confidence, the higher the requirements for their children, and the easier it is to stifle their children's creativity. On the contrary, families with a moderate education level are more likely to stimulate and protect their children's creativity.

There are significant differences in the mean innovation scores of college students with different family economic levels. This study distinguishes the level of household economic level according to the consumption level of college students. The measurement of the consumption level of college students adopts ordinal variables, which are divided into three categories: less than 1,000 yuan, 1,001-2,000 yuan, and more than 2,001

yuan. a level. The results of one-way ANOVA analysis showed that the significance value of the variance test was 0.652, and the variance was linear. There are significant differences in the mean innovation scores of college students at different consumption levels. The post-mortem test uses LSD. The data shows that the average innovation score of college students with a monthly consumption level of more than 2,001 yuan is the highest at 74.783, compared with a monthly consumption level of 1,001-2,000 yuan and a monthly consumption level of 1,000 yuan. The following college students have significant differences and the 95% confidence interval of the mean difference in innovation score with the college students whose consumption level is 1,001-2,000 yuan is 1.84-7.90, and the 95% confidence interval is 1.84-7.90. The 95% confidence interval of the mean difference of innovation scores was 2.55-9.12. The average innovation score of college students whose monthly consumption level is 1,001 to 2,000 yuan is not significantly different from that of college students whose consumption level is less than 1,000 yuan. See Figure 3-5.

平均值图

Figure 3-May Consumption Level and Innovation Score

- Training learning and innovation

When examining the correlation between college students' participation in training, classes and innovation scores, it is found that there is a significant difference in the mean innovation score between whether they have participated in art training before. Using the independent sample t-test to compare the innovation scores of students who have participated in art training and those who have never participated in art training, the average innovation score of students who have participated in art training is 70.54, and have never participated in art training. The average innovation score of college students is 68.24. The significance value of the Levine variance equality test result is 0.184, and the variance is linear. The corresponding mean value equality t test significance value is 0.019, which is less than 0.05, and there is a significant difference between the two. The 95% confidence interval of the difference was 0.386-4.219. Specifically examining the differences in the content of art training, it is found that there is a significant difference in the mean innovation scores of the college students who have studied dance and those who have not studied dance. . There was no significant difference in whether other arts types were trained or not. This shows that art training has a significant effect on improving the innovation ability of college students. The improvement of artistry is bound to foster innovation. Aesthetic education in art is also helpful for improving innovation.

In the investigation and analysis of different students who "have taken aesthetic education courses such as "Principles of Aesthetics", "Aesthetics and Aesthetic Education", etc., it is found that the innovation scores of students who have taken aesthetic education courses are significantly higher than those who have not taken aesthetic education courses. For students of education courses, the mean innovation score of college students who have taken aesthetic education courses is 71.98, with a standard deviation of 18.33, and the mean innovation score of college students who have not taken aesthetic education courses is 69.32, with a standard deviation of 16.73. One-way ANOVA analysis shows that the significance value of the Levine variance equality test result is 0.059, and the variance is linear, and the corresponding mean equality t-test significance (two-tailed) value is 0.28, indicating that he has taken aesthetic education as an elective. There is a significant difference in the mean innovation scores of college students who have not taken aesthetic education courses and

those who have not taken aesthetic education courses. The 95% confidence interval for the difference was 0.29 to 5.03. This shows that the learning of aesthetic education courses has a significant impact on the improvement of innovation. The specific data are shown in Table 3-3.

		独立样本检验								
		莱文方差等同性检验			平均值等同性 t 检验				差值 95% 置信区间	
		F	显著性	t	自由度	显著性 (双尾)	平均值差值	标准误差差值	下限	上限
创新总分百分制	假定等方差	3.583	.059	2.199	995	.028	2.65689	1.20832	.28575	5.02802
	不假定等方差			2.114	478.278	.035	2.65689	1.25701	.18695	5.12682

Table 3-3 Comparison of the mean values of aesthetic scores for elective aesthetic education courses

The mean innovation score of college students who have taken the compulsory course of ecological aesthetics is significantly higher than that of students who have not taken the compulsory course of ecological aesthetics. When asked, "Does your school offer a special required course for ecological aesthetics?", 31.5% answered that it did not offer it, 21.7% answered that it offered such a course, and 38.7% of college students chose to "Probably", and 8.1% chose "probably not". Students who answered that this course was offered should obviously have taken this course, while students who answered otherwise must not have taken the course. Tested by one-way ANOVA analysis, the variance is not linear, and the significance value of the mean equality robust test is 0.000, indicating that there is a significant difference in the mean of innovation scores between different answers. The data of Tammany and Dunnett's T3 test results are basically the same, and the mean innovation score of the college students who answered this compulsory course is significantly different from that of other types of respondents, and the significance values are 0.002, 0.000, and 0.025, respectively. There was no significant difference in the mean innovation scores of college students who answered "not offered", "may have", and "may not have". Comparing elective courses with compulsory courses, the importance of students' attention and credit requirements highlights the importance of aesthetic education courses in the proportion of compulsory courses, and provides a strong basis for us to strengthen innovation and aesthetic emphasis in compulsory courses. .

3.5 Status Quo of College Students' Aesthetic Literacy

For the measurement of aesthetic literacy, this study compiled an aesthetic literacy scale on the basis of reference to related research, which covers aesthetic knowledge, aesthetic ability, aesthetic awareness, aesthetic activities, and subjective evaluation of one's own aesthetic literacy. , a total of 10 items. The scale adopts 5-level scoring, and the respondents choose "strongly agree", "agree", "unclear", "disagree" and "strongly disagree" according to their own situation, and score according to the aesthetic dimension respectively. Divided into 1 to 5 points. After the total score of each item is converted into a percentile system, the score range is 0 to 100 points. The higher the score, the higher the aesthetic quality.

The aesthetic scores of the samples were counted. The sample mean was 76.45 points, the standard deviation was 17.89, the median was 75, the mode was 75, and the maximum was 100. The proportion of aesthetic scores below 50 points (including 50 points) is 11.0%, the proportion of scores above 80 points reaches 35.2%, of which the score of 100 points is as high as 15.8%. It can be seen that the overall level of aesthetic literacy of college students is relatively high.

- Gender and aesthetics

The analysis of the aesthetic scores of college students of different genders shows that the average aesthetic score of female college students is significantly higher than that of male college students. There are 718 female college students in the sample, with an average aesthetic score of 77.81, and 279 male college students with an average aesthetic score of 72.96, and the average difference is 4.85. The independent sample T test was used to analyze the two subjects. The results showed that the significance Sig value of the Levine variance equality test was 0.000, indicating that the variance of male and female college students' aesthetic scores was not equal, and the corresponding average value Equivalent t-test significance Sig value is 0.001, less than 0.05, there is a significant difference in the mean aesthetic scores of male college students and female college students. The 95% confidence interval of the difference is -7.64~-2.05.

Taking into account whether the students in art colleges may have an impact on aesthetic scores, the school type was used as a control variable to compare the average aesthetic scores of male students in art colleges and non-art colleges. The results show that among college students in art colleges, the average aesthetic score of boys is 70.25, the average aesthetic score of girls is 77.87, and the difference between the averages is 7.62. Independent sample t-test results: The Sig value of Levin's variance equality test is 0.037, the variance is not equal, and the corresponding mean equality t-test significance value is 0.007, and there is a significant difference between the average aesthetic scores of boys and girls , the confidence interval of the difference under the 95% confidence level is -13.09~-2.15. Among college students from non-art colleges, the average aesthetic score for boys was 73.92, and the average aesthetic score for girls was 77.79, with a difference of -3.86. The independent sample t-test results show that male and female college students have different aesthetic

total score variances, and the corresponding mean equivalence t-test significance value is 0.020, and there is a significant difference between the two means, with a 95% confidence interval for the difference. It is -7.12 to -0.6.

Similarly, in order to exclude the possible influence of art majors on aesthetic scores, the major category was used as a control variable, and the mean values of aesthetic scores of art majors and non-art majors were compared. Statistics show that among art college students, the average aesthetic score of boys is 74.48, the average aesthetic score of girls is 77.98, and the difference between the averages is -3.5, and the score of girls is higher than that of boys. The independent sample t-test results show that the significance value of the Levin's variance equality test is 0.019, the two-subject variance is not equal, and the corresponding mean-equivalent t-test significance sig value is 0.038, and the two-subject means are significantly different. Among non-art college students, the average aesthetic score of male students is 71.17, and the average aesthetic score of female students is 78.20, and the average difference is -7.03, which is also higher than that of male students. The independent sample t-test also demonstrated that there was a significant difference in mean aesthetic scores between boys and girls.

To sum up, it can be seen that the average level of aesthetic literacy of female college students is significantly higher than that of male college students.

- School type, major category and aesthetic quality

Statistics on the aesthetic literacy scores of college students in different types of schools show that the average aesthetic score of normal college students is the highest, at 78.04; the average aesthetic score of comprehensive school students is the lowest, at 75.45. The variance analysis shows that the average aesthetic scores of normal college students are significantly different from the average aesthetic scores of comprehensive college students, and there is no significant difference in the average aesthetic scores of students in other types of schools. Comparing the average aesthetic scores of college students in different major categories, art majors have the highest aesthetic score at 77.42; science and engineering students have the lowest aesthetic score at 74.60; liberal arts majors have the highest aesthetic score. The mean score was 77.36. The results of variance analysis show that there is no significant difference between the average aesthetic literacy of art majors and liberal arts majors, and there is a significant difference between the two and science majors. The average aesthetic scores of art majors and liberal arts majors are significantly higher than those of science majors. See Figure 3-6 and Table 3-4 for details.

多重比较

因变量: 审美总分百分制

	(i) 专业类别	(j) 专业类别	平均值差值 (i-j)	标准误差	显著性	95% 置信区间	
						下限	上限
LSD	文科类	理科类	2.76177 [*]	1.35809	.042	.0981	5.4254
		艺术类	-.05972	.94707	.950	-1.9173	1.7978
	理科类	文科类	-2.76177 [*]	1.35809	.042	-5.4254	-.0981
		艺术类	-2.82149 [*]	1.24120	.023	-5.2559	-.3871
	艺术类	文科类	.05972	.94707	.950	-1.7978	1.9173
		理科类	2.82149 [*]	1.24120	.023	.3871	5.2559

Table 3-4 Comparison of the mean values of aesthetic scores of different majors

Figure 3-6 Comparison of the aesthetic mean values of different professions

- Family background and aesthetic quality

College students with different family backgrounds have significant differences in the mean value of aesthetic scores. From the perspective of family location, the average aesthetic score of college students living in small cities is the highest, reaching 79.06; the average aesthetic score of college students living in rural areas is the lowest, 75.31. In the results of the one-way ANOVA analysis, the significance value of the variance test is 0.158, and the overall variance is equal. The mean square between the ANOVA groups is 1215.17, the mean square within the group is 292.56, and the significance value is 0.006, indicating that college students with different family locations have different aesthetics. The mean scores are significantly different. The specific differences can be seen from the LSD multiple comparison results. There is a significant difference in the mean aesthetic scores of college students whose families are located in small cities and those whose families are located in towns and villages; the mean scores were not significantly different from each other; the mean aesthetic scores of students living in large cities were not significantly different from the other categories.

From the perspective of the cultural level of the parents, there is a significant difference in the mean aesthetic scores of their children with the difference in parental education. Parental education is used as a factor to conduct a one-way ANOVA test of aesthetic scores. The significance value of the variance test is 0.006, and the variance is not equal. A robust test of equality of the mean values of Mulch is carried out, and its significance value is 0.006. 0.002, it can be seen that there are significant differences in the mean aesthetic scores of their children with different educational backgrounds. The sample mean: college students whose parents' education is high school/secondary school have the highest aesthetic score, those whose mother's education is junior high school and below have the lowest aesthetic score, and those whose parents' education is junior college and bachelor's degree or above. The score is between the two. The multiple comparisons between Tam and Dunnett's T3 show that the average aesthetic score of college students whose parental education is high school/secondary school is significantly higher than that of college students whose parental education is junior high school and below. Its significance value is 0.001. Although the average aesthetic value of college students whose parental education is junior high school and below is higher than that of college students whose parental education is junior high school and below, its significance value is greater than 0.05, which is not statistically significant. The sample mean shows that the difference in parental education and the change in the aesthetic mean of college students show a certain regularity. With the increase of parental education, the sample mean also increases. 0.511, there is no statistically significant difference between the categories.

Differences in the nature of college students' parenting work also have significant differences in the mean values of their children's aesthetic scores. For college students whose parents' work unit is a state-owned unit, the sample average value of aesthetic score is 78.60, which is higher than several other categories. See Figure 3-7 for details. Through one-way analysis of variance, we can see that the overall variance is linear, the mean square between the groups is 893.116 ANOVA is much larger than the mean square within the group 293.127, the significance value is 0.028, and the mean value of the aesthetic scores of college students with different parents' work nature has significant difference. The LSD multiple comparison results show that the mean aesthetic scores of college students whose parents work in the state are significantly different from those whose

parents belong to families and the other two categories. The 95% confidence intervals for the difference between the mean scores were 0.073 to 4.61 and 0.704 to 5.61, respectively.

Figure 3-7 Total score of father's work and aesthetics

The relationship between the nature of pro-work unit and the mean of college students' aesthetic scores also showed significant differences between different categories. The significance value of the mean equality robust test is 0.003. In the sample mean, the college students whose pro-work units belong to the private sector have the highest scores. Multiple comparisons of Tamney and Dunnett's T3 both show pro-work. There is a significant difference between the average aesthetic scores of college students whose work unit belongs to the private sector, and the other two types of college students whose parents work as a family. The former is significantly higher than the latter.

From the perspective of family economic level, the higher the economic level, the higher the average aesthetic score of college students. This study measures the household economic level of college students by asking their monthly consumption amount, which is divided into three levels: the monthly consumption amount is less than 1,000 yuan, the monthly consumption amount is 1,001-2,000 yuan, and the monthly consumption amount is more than 2,001 yuan. Frequency distribution analysis statistics show that in the sample, the monthly consumption amount is less than 1,000 yuan, accounting for 24.6%; the monthly consumption amount is between 1,001 and 2,000 yuan, accounting for 67.9%; the monthly consumption amount is more than 2,001 yuan, 7.5%. The proportion of boys with a monthly consumption of more than 2,001 yuan is higher than that of girls, and the monthly consumption is significantly related to the location of their family. The proportion of college students whose home is in a big city has a monthly consumption of more than 2,001 yuan than other categories. The proportion of college students living in small cities with monthly consumption between 1,001 and 2,000 yuan is the highest among all categories, while the proportion of college students living in rural areas with monthly consumption of less than 1,000 yuan is the highest among all categories. One-way ANOVA analysis was performed on the mean values of aesthetic scores of college students with different consumption levels. The variance test showed that the significance value was 0.307, and the overall variance was equal. , the F value is 7.947, and the significance value is 0.000, indicating that the average aesthetic scores of college students with different consumption levels are significantly different. The data are shown in Table 3-5.

多重比较

因变量: 审美总分百分制

LSD	(I) 每月消费	(J) 每月消费	平均值差值 (I-J)	标准误差	显著性	95% 置信区间	
						下限	上限
	1000元以下	1001~2000元	-2.26470 [*]	.97056	.020	-4.1683	-.3611
		2001元以上	-6.73608 [*]	1.72374	.000	-10.1169	-3.3552
	1001~2000元	1000元以下	2.26470 [*]	.97056	.020	.3611	4.1683
		2001元以上	-4.47138 [*]	1.59068	.005	-7.5913	-1.3515
	2001元以上	1000元以下	6.73608 [*]	1.72374	.000	3.3552	10.1169
		1001~2000元	4.47138 [*]	1.59068	.005	1.3515	7.5913

Table 3-5 Comparison of the average aesthetic values of college students with different consumption levels

The least significant difference (LSD) was used for the post-hoc comparison. The data are shown in the table. The significance of the mean difference between each category is less than 0.05, and there is a significant difference between each category. The mean value graph shows that as the consumption level rises, the mean value of aesthetic scores also increases, and the two are positively correlated. See Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8 Consumption level and total aesthetic score

- Art training and aesthetic literacy

In order to examine the impact of art training on the aesthetic literacy of college students, this study counted the previous art training of the sample, and statistically analyzed the differences between the aesthetic scores of college students in different training situations. In the sample, 9.4% of college students have studied vocal music, 16.7% of college students have studied instrumental music, 60.4% of college students have studied calligraphy or art, 14.5% of college students have studied dance, and 12.6% of college students have never received any type of art training. Among them, 13.9% of college students have received two types of art training, 6.2% of college students have received 3 types of art training, and 2.6% of college students have received more than 4 types of art training.

Through the independent sample T test to compare the average aesthetic scores of college students who have never learned any art specialties and those who have studied art specialties, the data shows that the average value of the sample aesthetic scores of college students who have never studied is 74.88, and the average value of the aesthetic score sample of college students who have studied art specialties is 77.61. The significance of the Levine variance equality test is set at 0.040, the variances are not equal, and the corresponding mean equality t test significance value is 0.005, which is less than 0.05, indicating the aesthetic scores of the students who have studied and have never studied. The means are significantly different. The 95% confidence interval of the difference is -4.61 to -0.84.

Statistical comparison of the aesthetic scores of college students who have studied vocal music shows that the significance value of the mean equivalence t-test is 0.329, which is greater than 0.05, and there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the two students. For the statistical comparison of the aesthetic scores of the college students who have studied instrumental music or not, the significance value of the t-test of the mean value is 0.961, which is greater than 0.05, and there is no significant difference between the two groups.

An independent sample T-test was conducted on the aesthetic scores of college students who had studied calligraphy/art. The average value of the samples of college students who had studied calligraphy/art was 78.57, and the sample of college students who had not studied calligraphy/art was 78.57. The mean value is 74.65, the mean difference value is 3.92, the significance value of the Levine variance equality test is 0.719, greater than 0.05, the variance is equal, and the corresponding mean value equality t test significance value is 0.000, less than 0.05, there is a significant difference between the two. The 95% confidence interval for the difference was 2.24 to 5.60. The average aesthetic score of college students who have studied calligraphy/art is significantly higher than that of college students who have not studied. Similarly, an independent sample t-test was conducted on the average aesthetic score of college students who had studied dance. The average value of the sample aesthetic score of college students who had studied dance was 81.97, and the sample average value of aesthetic score of college students who had not studied dance was 76.18. , the mean difference value is 5.79, the significance value of the Levine variance equality test is 0.707, greater than 0.05, the overall equal variance, and the corresponding mean value equality t test significance value is 0.000, less than 0.05, two are significantly different. The 95% confidence interval for the difference was 3.49 to 8.08. The average aesthetic score of college students who have studied dance is significantly higher than that of college students who have not studied dance.

A bivariate correlation analysis was conducted between the number of college students' learning art specialties and the college students' aesthetic scores, and the results showed that the two were significantly positively correlated at the level of 0.01, with a correlation coefficient of 0.115. That is, the more types of art specialties college students learn, the higher the corresponding aesthetic score. One-way ANOVA analysis was used to compare the mean values of aesthetic scores in each group, the significance value of variance test was 0.215, and the overall variance was equal. The sex value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and there is a significant difference in the mean value of aesthetic scores among the categories. The sample mean shows that the average aesthetic score of college students who have studied 5 kinds of art specialties is the highest, which is 85.42, and the average aesthetic score of college students who have never studied is the lowest, only 74.91. See Figure 3-9 for details.

Figure 3-9 Types of art training and total aesthetic scores

- Aesthetic education curriculum and aesthetic literacy

The establishment of college aesthetic education courses should have a positive impact on the improvement of college students' aesthetic literacy. What is the current situation of the establishment of Chinese aesthetic

education courses in colleges and universities, and does it play a role in improving the aesthetic quality of college students? In this study, questionnaires were used to inquire about the opening of aesthetic education courses in the schools where the respondents were located, and take this as an independent variable to compare the differences in aesthetic scores of college students in different states.

According to the survey data, when asked "Have you taken courses in aesthetic education such as "Principles of Aesthetics", "Aesthetics and Aesthetic Education", etc., 28.2% of college students answered that they had taken elective courses, and 71.8% of them had not taken elective courses. Pass. When asked, "Does your school offer a special required course for ecological aesthetics?", 31.5% of the respondents answered that they did not offer such a course, 21.7% answered that such a course was offered, and 38.7% of college students chose to "Possibly", and 8.1% chose "probably not". When asked, "Does your school offer a general elective course in ecological aesthetics?", 26.2% of the college students said "no", 22.4% of the college students answered "yes", and 43.7% of the college students answered "yes". Students answered "probably yes" and 7.6% of college students answered "probably not". The answers to these three questions and the type of school where the sample is located are cross-tabulated. The results show that there is no significant difference in the responses of college students from different types of schools to whether they have taken elective courses in aesthetic education, such as "Principles of Aesthetics" and "Aesthetic Education"; there are significant differences in the responses of students from different types of schools. Cross-tabular chi-square test was performed on whether to offer compulsory courses in ecological aesthetics and the type of school. The pilson chi-square asymptotic significance value was 0.000. The proportion is the highest at 31.3%, and the proportion of students in art schools answering to offer related courses is the lowest, only 18.7%. Regarding the answer to whether there are elective courses in ecological aesthetics, the chi-square test results are consistent with the analysis of whether compulsory courses are offered, and the pilson chi-square asymptotic significance value is 0.000. There are significant differences in whether different types of schools offer relevant courses. The differences are also the same as the differences in whether to offer compulsory courses in ecological aesthetics. The proportion of comprehensive college students who answered that they offered relevant courses was the highest at 31.7%, and the proportion of art college students who answered that they offered relevant courses, the lowest, only 17.6%.

Comparing the mean value of aesthetic scores of college students who have taken aesthetic education courses and those who have not taken aesthetic education courses, the independent sample T test results show that the aesthetic education of college students who have taken aesthetic education courses The mean value of the score sample is 78.05, the mean value of the aesthetic score sample of the college students who have not taken aesthetic education courses is 76.61, the mean value difference is 1.44, the significance value of the Levine variance equality test is 0.876, the overall variance is equal, and the corresponding mean equality t-test significance value is 0.117, which is greater than 0.05, and there is no significant difference between the two. There is no significant difference in the mean of aesthetic scores between college students who have taken aesthetic education courses and those who have not taken aesthetic education courses. The data are shown in Table 3-6.

		独立样本检验							
		莱文方差等同性检验		平均值等同性 t 检验					
		F	显著性	t	自由度	显著性 (双尾)	平均值差值	标准误差差值	差值 95% 置信区间 下限 上限
审美总分百分制	假定等方差	.024	.876	1.568	1713	.117	1.44197	.91982	-.36210 3.24605
	不假定等方差			1.566	882.176	.118	1.44197	.92065	-.36494 3.24889

Table 3-6 Comparison of the mean values of aesthetic scores for elective aesthetic courses

The mean value of aesthetic scores of college students who answered different answers to "Whether to offer an elective course of ecological aesthetics general education" was counted and compared by one-way ANOVA analysis. The results showed that the significance value of variance test was 0.054, and the square The differences are equal, the mean square between the ANOVA groups is 555.846, the mean square within the group is 293.719, the significance value is 0.129, greater than 0.05, and there is no significant difference between the mean values of aesthetic scores of different respondents.

Statistical comparison of the mean aesthetic scores of different respondents in "Whether to offer a compulsory course of ecological aesthetics", the one-way ANOVA analysis results show that the variance test significance value is 0.059, the variance is equal, and the mean square between ANOVA groups is 2305.978, the mean square within the group is 290.650, and the significance value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. There is a significant difference between the mean values of aesthetic scores of different respondents. The analysis data are shown in Table 3-7.

ANOVA					
审美总分百分制					
	平方和	自由度	均方	F	显著性
组间	6917.935	3	2305.978	7.934	.000
组内	497302.386	1711	290.650		
总计	504220.322	1714			

Table 3-7 Analysis of variance results

The least significant difference (LSD) was used to conduct multiple comparisons, and the results showed that the average aesthetic scores of the college students who answered the compulsory course of ecological aesthetics were significantly different from the average scores of the respondents in other categories. There was no significant difference between. The comparison of mean values is shown in Figure 3-10 and Table 3-8.

多重比较							
因变量: 审美总分百分制							
	(i) 1.14 您所在的学校是否开设有专门的生态美学的必修课?	(j) 1.14 您所在的学校是否开设有专门的生态美学的必修课?	平均值差值 (i-j)	标准误差	显著性	95% 置信区间	
						下限	上限
LSD	A没有	B有	-3.68354*	1.14872	.001	-5.9366	-1.4305
		C可能有	1.69508	.98791	.086	-.2426	3.6327
		D可能没有	-.08672	1.62150	.957	-3.2670	3.0936
	B有	A没有	3.68354*	1.14872	.001	1.4305	5.9366
		C可能有	5.37862*	1.10410	.000	3.2131	7.5442
		D可能没有	3.59682*	1.69479	.034	.2727	6.9209
	C可能有	A没有	-1.69508	.98791	.086	-3.6327	.2426
		B有	-5.37862*	1.10410	.000	-7.5442	-3.2131
		D可能没有	-1.78180	1.59020	.263	-4.9007	1.3371
	D可能没有	A没有	.08672	1.62150	.957	-3.0936	3.2670
		B有	-3.59682*	1.69479	.034	-6.9209	-.2727
		C可能有	1.78180	1.59020	.263	-1.3371	4.9007

*. 平均值差值的显著性水平为 0.05。

Table 3-8 Comparison of the mean scores of the compulsory courses of ecological aesthetics

平均值图

Figure 3-10 Comparison of the mean values of aesthetic scores for the compulsory courses of ecological aesthetics

As for whether there are elective courses in ecological aesthetics and whether there are compulsory courses in ecological aesthetics, students who answered "yes (yes)" should generally have taken electives or have taken the corresponding courses, and answered "no", "maybe" Yes" and "probably not" students must have never attended such courses. Therefore, it can be seen that whether the school offers aesthetic education courses has no effect on the aesthetic scores of college students, whether college students have taken the general elective courses of ecological aesthetics has no effect on the aesthetic scores, and whether they have studied the compulsory courses of ecological aesthetics It has a significant impact on the aesthetic scores of college students. The average aesthetic score of college students who have taken the compulsory course of ecological aesthetics is significantly higher than that of students who have not taken such courses.

3.6 Innovation, ecological outlook and aesthetic quality

For college students in art colleges (major), the cultivation and improvement of aesthetic literacy is the need for professional study and future employment. According to the analysis of the current situation of college students' ecological aesthetic literacy, it can be seen that the main factors affecting college students' aesthetic literacy are gender, school type, major category, family location, parental cultural level, parental occupation, and family economy. Level, art training and learning situation, ecological aesthetic education professional course learning situation, etc. The learning and training of artistic skills requires a certain creative ability, and artistic creation has higher requirements for innovation. Therefore, innovation and aesthetic literacy should be inherently unified, and the two are based on each other and promote each other. At the same time, the understanding and pursuit of natural ecological balance should have a positive effect on the improvement of aesthetic literacy, and ecological outlook and aesthetic literacy should also promote each other.

- Correlation analysis of aesthetic literacy, innovation and ecological outlook

The aesthetic score, innovation score and ecological score of college students were tested by SPSS bivariate correlation analysis. The results showed that the three were significantly correlated at the 0.01 level (two-tailed). The correlation coefficient between the aesthetic score and the ecological score is 0.329, and the correlation coefficient with the innovation score is 0.631, indicating a high degree of correlation. The correlation coefficient between ecological score and innovation score is 0.159, which is slightly weaker. For specific data, see Table 3-9.

相关性

	生态得分	审美总分	创新总分
生态得分	1		
审美总分	.329**	1	
创新总分	.159**	.631**	1

** . 在 0.01 级别 (双尾) , 相关性显著。

Table 3-9 Correlation analysis results

It can be seen that the ecological score, innovation score and aesthetic score are positively correlated with each other, the aesthetic score has the highest correlation with the innovation score, and the ecological score has a relatively weak correlation with the innovation score. The higher the ecological score, the higher the aesthetic score, and the higher the innovation score. Likewise, the higher the aesthetic score, the higher the innovation score and the ecological score. The three are inherently unified, based on each other, and promote each other.

- Regression analysis of aesthetic literacy

This study uses regression analysis to try to build a regression model of aesthetic scores. The aesthetic score is used as the dependent variable, and the innovation score, ecological score, family situation, professional category, school type, gender, art training and other variables are used as independent variables. The variables of family situation include family location, parent's education, parent's occupation, and monthly consumption level. Variables such as family location, family education, family occupation, monthly consumption level, professional category, school type, gender, art training and other variables are categorical and ordinal variables, so first convert these variables into dummy variables, family location Converted to 3 dummy variables, household occupation converted to 6 dummy variables (parents 3 and parents 3), parent education converted to 6 dummy variables, monthly consumption level converted to 2 dummy variables, art Training was converted into 4 dummy variables, and professional category, school type, gender, etc. were each converted into 1 dummy variable, and a total of 26 independent variables participated in the regression analysis.

The regression analysis first adopts the forced entry strategy (Enter) and performs multicollinearity detection. The model summary shows that the adjusted coefficient of determination is 0.489, and the goodness of fit is moderate. See Table 3-10 for details.

模型摘要^b

模型	R	R 方	调整后 R 方	标准估算的误差	德宾-沃森
1	.706 ^a	.498	.489	12.20350	1.253

a. 预测变量: (常量), 1.12 是否学过舞蹈), Q14=B有, consum=1001~2000元, 是否艺术类院校, q6new=大专, Q5=城镇, 生态价值观, mojob=私营, q7new=本科及以上, Q1=B女, q7new=高中|中专, 1.12 是否学过声乐), fajob=家庭, Q5=省会等大城市, 创新总分百分制, 1.12 是否学过器乐), 1.12 是否学过书法|美术), q7new=大专, 生态得分百分制, q6new=高中|中专, consum=2001元以上, fajob=私营, mojob=国有, q6new=本科及以上, Q5=中小城市, 是否艺术类专业, mojob=家庭, fajob=国有

b. 因变量: 审美总分百分制

Table 3-10 Model Summaries

The ANOVA results show that the total squared deviation of the explained variable is 451630.859, the regression sum and mean square are 224817.345 and 8029.191 respectively, the residual sum and mean squares are 226813.514 and 148.925 respectively, the observation of the F test statistic A value of 53.914 corresponds to a probability p-value of approximately 0. The data are shown in Table 3-11. The data are shown in Table 3.11. Since the probability p value is less than the significance level α , the null hypothesis of the significance test of the regression equation should be rejected, and it is considered that the regression coefficients are not equal to 0 at the same time, and the linear relationship between the explained variable and the entire explanatory variable is significant and can be established, the Linear model.

ANOVA^a

模型		平方和	自由度	均方	F	显著性
1	回归	224817.345	28	8029.191	53.914	.000 ^b
	残差	226813.514	1523	148.925		
	总计	451630.859	1551			

a. 因变量: 审美总分百分制

b. 预测变量: (常量), 1.12 是否学过舞蹈), Q14=B有, consum=1001~2000元, 是否艺术类院校, q6new=大专, Q5=城镇, 生态价值观, mojob=私营, q7new=本科及以上, Q1=B女, q7new=高中|中专, 1.12 是否学过声乐), fajob=家庭, Q5=省会等大城市, 创新总分百分制, 1.12 是否学过器乐), 1.12 是否学过书法|美术), q7new=大专, 生态得分百分制, q6new=高中|中专, consum=2001元以上, fajob=私营, mojob=国有, q6new=本科及以上, Q5=中小城市, 是否艺术类专业, mojob=家庭, fajob=国有

Table 3.11 Significance test of regression equation

The regression coefficient of each variable was tested, and it was found that the probability p value of the significant t-test of the regression coefficient of some variables was greater than the significance level α , such as family location, art school, parental education, parental occupation, whether Having studied instrumental music and dance, etc., the linear relationship between these variables and aesthetic scores is not significant and should not be retained in the equation and should be remodeled. The data are shown in Table 3-12.

系数^a

模型		未标准化系数		标准化系数	t	显著性	共线性统计	
		B	标准错误	Beta			容差	VIF
1	(常量)	2.698	2.451		1.100	.271		
	生态得分百分制	.191	.028	.146	6.835	.000	.727	1.375
	创新总分百分制	.546	.020	.531	26.685	.000	.831	1.203
	Q1=B女	3.848	.891	.081	4.319	.000	.938	1.067
	1.12 是否学过书法(美术)	4.566	.866	.128	5.269	.000	.558	1.791
	Q5=中小城市	1.073	.915	.029	1.172	.241	.532	1.880
	Q14=B有	1.852	.784	.044	2.362	.018	.947	1.056
	是否艺术类专业	-2.837	.927	-.080	-3.061	.002	.484	2.068
	生态价值观	.204	.026	.170	7.711	.000	.679	1.473
	是否艺术类院校	-.385	.784	-.010	-.491	.623	.754	1.326
	q6new=高中 中专	-2.289	.850	-.061	-2.694	.007	.636	1.574
	q6new=大专	-.262	1.427	-.004	-.184	.854	.623	1.606
	q6new=本科及以上	-.932	1.590	-.014	-.586	.558	.557	1.794
	q7new=高中 中专	1.011	.851	.027	1.188	.235	.640	1.563
	q7new=大专	.131	1.590	.002	.082	.934	.660	1.514
	q7new=本科及以上	.895	1.637	.014	.547	.584	.539	1.854
	fajob=国有	1.572	1.284	.038	1.224	.221	.347	2.885
	fajob=私营	.156	1.144	.004	.137	.891	.390	2.567
	fajob=家庭	.373	1.115	.010	.334	.738	.352	2.842
	mojob=国有	-1.174	1.365	-.026	-.861	.390	.367	2.723
	mojob=私营	2.532	1.222	.059	2.071	.038	.410	2.440
	mojob=家庭	.826	1.061	.024	.779	.436	.350	2.861
	Q5=省会等大城市	-.403	1.235	-.007	-.326	.744	.635	1.575
	Q5=城镇	.295	.853	.008	.346	.729	.612	1.635
	consum=2001元以上	1.723	1.416	.027	1.217	.224	.676	1.479
	consum=1001~2000元	-.029	.794	-.001	-.036	.971	.715	1.399
	1.12 是否学过声乐)	3.085	1.144	.053	2.697	.007	.840	1.191
	1.12 是否学过器乐)	-.740	.928	-.016	-.797	.426	.797	1.255
	1.12 是否学过舞蹈)	1.543	1.012	.031	1.525	.128	.785	1.274

a. 因变量：审美总分百分制

Table 3-12 Regression coefficients

Model again, use a stepwise screening strategy, and perform residual analysis. The step-by-step screening strategy has a total of 10 steps to complete the establishment of the regression equation, and the final model is the tenth model. See Table 3.13.

系数^a

模型		未标准化系数		标准化系数	t	显著性	共线性统计	
		B	标准错误	Beta			容差	VIF
1	(常量)	2.698	2.451		1.100	.271		
	生态得分百分制	.191	.028	.146	6.835	.000	.727	1.375
	创新总分百分制	.546	.020	.531	26.685	.000	.831	1.203
	Q1=B女	3.848	.891	.081	4.319	.000	.938	1.067
	1.12 是否学过书法(美术)	4.566	.866	.128	5.269	.000	.558	1.791
	Q5=中小城市	1.073	.915	.029	1.172	.241	.532	1.880
	Q14=B有	1.852	.784	.044	2.362	.018	.947	1.056
	是否艺术类专业	-2.837	.927	-.080	-3.061	.002	.484	2.068
	生态价值观	.204	.026	.170	7.711	.000	.679	1.473
	是否艺术类院校	-.385	.784	-.010	-.491	.623	.754	1.326
	q6new=高中 中专	-2.289	.850	-.061	-2.694	.007	.636	1.574
	q6new=大专	-.262	1.427	-.004	-.184	.854	.623	1.606
	q6new=本科及以上	-.932	1.590	-.014	-.586	.558	.557	1.794
	q7new=高中 中专	1.011	.851	.027	1.188	.235	.640	1.563
	q7new=大专	.131	1.590	.002	.082	.934	.660	1.514
	q7new=本科及以上	.895	1.637	.014	.547	.584	.539	1.854
	fajob=国有	1.572	1.284	.038	1.224	.221	.347	2.885
	fajob=私营	.156	1.144	.004	.137	.891	.390	2.567
	fajob=家庭	.373	1.115	.010	.334	.738	.352	2.842
	mojob=国有	-1.174	1.365	-.026	-.861	.390	.367	2.723
	mojob=私营	2.532	1.222	.059	2.071	.038	.410	2.440
	mojob=家庭	.826	1.061	.024	.779	.436	.350	2.861
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	Q5=城镇	.295	.853	.008	.346	.729	.612	1.635
	consum=2001元以上	1.723	1.416	.027	1.217	.224	.676	1.479
	consum=1001~2000元	-.029	.794	-.001	-.036	.971	.715	1.399
	1.12 是否学过声乐)	3.085	1.144	.053	2.697	.007	.840	1.191
	1.12 是否学过器乐)	-.740	.928	-.016	-.797	.426	.797	1.255
	1.12 是否学过舞蹈)	1.543	1.012	.031	1.525	.128	.785	1.274

a. 因变量：审美总分百分制

Table 3-13 Final Model Summaries

From the point of view of the establishment process of the equation, with the continuous screening of explanatory variables, the goodness of fit of the equation finally reaches the optimal result. The adjusted coefficient of determination is 0.490, and the goodness of fit of the equation is good. The Durbin-Watson test value is 1.250, indicating that the residuals have a certain degree of positive autocorrelation. For detailed data, see Table 3-14.

模型		平方和	自由度	均方	F	显著性
1	回归	176056.180	1	176056.180	990.247	.000 ^b
	残差	275574.680	1550	177.790		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
2	回归	201737.066	2	100868.533	625.247	.000 ^c
	残差	249893.794	1549	161.326		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
3	回归	210372.032	3	70124.011	449.940	.000 ^d
	残差	241258.828	1548	155.852		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
4	回归	213718.374	4	53429.594	347.420	.000 ^e
	残差	237912.485	1547	153.790		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
5	回归	216431.621	5	43286.324	284.528	.000 ^f
	残差	235199.239	1546	152.134		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
6	回归	218122.741	6	36353.790	240.534	.000 ^g
	残差	233508.118	1545	151.138		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
7	回归	219644.647	7	31377.807	208.837	.000 ^h
	残差	231986.212	1544	150.250		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
8	回归	220986.110	8	27623.264	184.798	.000 ⁱ
	残差	230644.749	1543	149.478		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
9	回归	221945.648	9	24660.628	165.560	.000 ^j
	残差	229685.212	1542	148.953		
	总计	451630.859	1551			
10	回归	222609.928	10	22260.993	149.786	.000 ^k
	残差	229020.931	1541	148.618		
	总计	451630.859	1551			

Table 3-14 Significance test of regression equation (final)

a. Dependent variable: aesthetic total score percentile system

b. Predictor variables: (constant), innovation total score percentile

c. Predictor variables: (constant), innovation total score percentile, ecological score percentile

d. Predictor variables: (constant), innovation total score percentile system, ecological score percentile system, ecological values

e. Predictor variables: (constant), innovation total score percentile, ecological score percentile, ecological values, 1.12

Have you studied calligraphy | art)

f. Predictor variables: (constant), innovation total score percentile system, ecological score percentile system, ecological values, 1.12 Have you studied calligraphy | art), Q1=B woman

g. Predictor variables: (constant), total innovation score percentile system, ecological score percentile system, ecological values, 1.12 whether you have studied calligraphy | art), Q1=B, whether art majors

h. Predictor variables: (constant), innovation total score percentile system, ecological score percentile system, ecological values, 1.12 Did you learn calligraphy|

The tenth model is the final equation, the probability p value of the regression equation significance test is less than the significance level α , so the linear relationship between the explained variable and the explanatory variable is significant, and it is appropriate to build a linear model. The partial regression coefficient of each explanatory variable in the equation and the probability p value of the significance test of the partial regression coefficient are shown in Table 3-15:

10	(常量)	2.869	2.314		1.240	.215		
	创新总分百分制	.550	.020	.535	27.174	.000	.848	1.179
	生态得分百分制	.201	.028	.153	7.278	.000	.748	1.337
	生态价值观	.203	.026	.169	7.785	.000	.696	1.438
	1.12 是否学过书法(美术)	4.967	.822	.139	6.040	.000	.618	1.617
	Q1=B女	3.866	.873	.081	4.427	.000	.974	1.027
	是否艺术类专业	3.076	.822	.087	3.743	.000	.614	1.629
	1.12 是否学过声乐)	3.377	1.066	.058	3.168	.002	.966	1.036
	mojob=私营	2.654	.795	.062	3.337	.001	.966	1.035
	Q14=B有	1.972	.775	.047	2.544	.011	.967	1.035
	q6new=高中 中专	1.451	.686	.039	2.114	.035	.972	1.029

a. 因变量：审美总分百分制

Table 3-15 Regression Coefficient Test (Final Equation)

The p-values of the regression coefficient significance test probability of each explanatory variable are all less than the α value (0.05), and there is a significant linear relationship with the aesthetic score of the explained variable, which should be retained in the equation. The tolerance and variance inflation factor data show no multicollinearity. Table 3-16 are the variables excluded from the model.

10	Q5=中小城市	.031 ^k	1.685	.092	.043	.964	1.038	.611
	是否艺术类院校	-.006 ^k	-.273	.785	-.007	.766	1.306	.525
	q6new=大专	.011 ^k	.593	.553	.015	.955	1.048	.614
	q6new=本科及以上	-.007 ^k	-.376	.707	-.010	.924	1.082	.607
	q7new=高中 中专	.028 ^k	1.370	.171	.035	.800	1.251	.613
	q7new=大专	.000 ^k	-.027	.978	-.001	.985	1.015	.614
	q7new=本科及以上	-.005 ^k	-.259	.795	-.007	.975	1.026	.614
	fajob=国有	.021 ^k	1.116	.264	.028	.958	1.044	.605
	fajob=私营	-.010 ^k	-.489	.625	-.012	.781	1.281	.614
	fajob=家庭	.012 ^k	.655	.513	.017	.934	1.071	.613
	mojob=国有	-.012 ^k	-.621	.535	-.016	.911	1.098	.601
	mojob=家庭	.030 ^k	1.472	.141	.037	.811	1.234	.614
	Q5=省会等大城市	-.013 ^k	-.684	.494	-.017	.962	1.040	.610
	Q5=城镇	-.007 ^k	-.369	.712	-.009	.976	1.025	.611
	consum=2001元以上	.030 ^k	1.604	.109	.041	.943	1.061	.610
	consum=1001~2000元	-.014 ^k	-.771	.441	-.020	.952	1.051	.611
	1.12 是否学过器乐)	-.003 ^k	-.148	.883	-.004	.914	1.094	.613
	1.12 是否学过舞蹈)	.031 ^k	1.603	.109	.041	.874	1.144	.592

Table 3-16 Variables excluded from the model

a. Dependent variable: Percentage system of aesthetic total score

k. Predictive variables in the model: (constant), innovation total score percentile system, ecological score percentile system, ecological values, 1.12 Have you studied calligraphy | art), Q1=B, whether you are an art major, 1.12 Have you studied vocal music), mojob=private, Q14=B has, q6new= high school | technical secondary school

The final regression equation is:

Aesthetic total score = 2.869 + 0.55 total innovation score + 0.201 total ecological score + 0.203 ecological value score + 4.967 whether you have studied calligraphy and art + 3.866 whether you have studied female sex + 3.377 whether you have studied vocal music + 2.654 whether you are a pro-professional private unit + 1.972 Whether the school offers ecological aesthetics courses + 3.076 Whether the art major + 1.451 The parent's education is high school

It can be seen from the equation that for every increase of 1 point in the total innovation score, the total aesthetic score increases by 0.55 points, for every increase in the ecological total score by 1 point, the aesthetic total score increases by 0.201 points, and the ecological value increases by 1 point, the aesthetic total score increases by 0.203 points. The students who have studied calligraphy and art are 4.987 points higher than those who have not studied it, the girls are 3.866 points higher than the boys, and the students who have studied vocal music are 3.377 points higher. Students in the aesthetics course scored 1.972 points higher. Art majors will score 3.076 higher, and those whose parents have a high school education will score 1.451 higher.

Statistical analysis of the residual data shows that,

Figure 3-11 Normalized P-P plot of standardized residuals

The data points still have certain regularity around the baseline, but the non-parametric test results of the standardized residuals show that there is no significant difference between the standardized residuals and the standard normal distribution, and it can be considered that the residuals meet the premise of the linear model. See Figure 3-11, Figure 3-12 and Table 3-17.

残差统计^a

	最小值	最大值	平均值	标准偏差	个案数
预测值	12.9540	104.5617	77.3437	11.98026	1552
标准预测值	-5.375	2.272	.000	1.000	1552
预测值的标准误差	.559	2.268	.993	.258	1552
调整后预测值	12.8024	104.6931	77.3433	11.97405	1552
残差	-92.74900	39.24828	.00000	12.15155	1552
标准残差	-7.608	3.219	.000	.997	1552
学生化残差	-7.650	3.240	.000	1.001	1552
删除残差	-93.76747	39.75172	.00047	12.24805	1552
学生化删除残差	-7.797	3.250	.000	1.003	1552
马氏距离	2.258	52.674	9.994	6.142	1552
库克距离	.000	.058	.001	.002	1552
居中杠杆值	.001	.034	.006	.004	1552

a. 因变量: 审美总分百分制

Table 3-17 Residual Statistics

Figure 3-12 Scatter plot of standardized residuals

3.7 Research conclusions

(1) Paying attention to the relevant variables and main influencing factors of students' ecological aesthetic literacy is the key to improving ecological aesthetic literacy

According to the research results, innovation literacy has a significant influence on aesthetic literacy; ecological literacy also has a significant influence on aesthetic literacy; the improvement of ecological values also has a significant influence on aesthetic ability.

Aesthetic literacy is inextricably linked with innovation literacy and ecological literacy, and the three promote and build on each other. College students have a strong sense of aesthetics, and there are obvious differences in many dimensions, such as men and women, parents' educational background, family income, art training, and ecological aesthetics courses.

(2) The existing curriculum system still cannot meet the ecological aesthetic education requirements of art students

The needs of college students' aesthetic education courses in art education, aesthetic education of subject majors and interdisciplinary aesthetic education show the following characteristics: ① Nearly 40% of college students have not learned art skills and techniques; ② The art skills training received by college students is mainly concentrated before high school, mainly in the fields of music, art and dance, off-campus tutoring and self-study are important ways for college students to train in art; ③ The main purpose of college students

learning art skills is to improve their aesthetic ability and hope to acquire a variety of artistic skills for self-entertainment; ④ Most college students like themselves Most of the majors do not offer corresponding aesthetic courses, and even lack attention to ecological aesthetics in elective courses; ⑤ College students have a certain understanding of the cross-border existence of beauty, mainly focusing on nature and in the field of art.

(3) An innovative, interactive, integrated and developed multi-ecological aesthetic education curriculum design should be constructed

The aesthetic education work in colleges and universities has gradually become an indispensable link in the cultivation of senior talents. The design of aesthetic education courses in colleges and universities is a very complex systematic project, which involves the cooperation between various departments, functional personnel, teachers and even students within the university. In view of the regularity of university development itself and the current state of universities in the current economic and social conditions, this process has to rely on the support of the school system, teaching staff and modern information technology.

- Innovation

The goal of the ecological aesthetic education course ultimately points to the cultivation of innovation ability. Artistic creation emphasizes imagination and creativity. The image thinking of art provides people with new ideas and is the source of creativity. Reasonably plan the target training system of ecological aesthetic education, and make a staged curriculum target system division for the final training of innovative artistic talents. According to the division of the school year, the curriculum target system of ecological aesthetic education is divided into the first, second, and cognitive stages. The basis of ecological aesthetic education for design majors is conducive to the improvement of students' aesthetic literacy, and its purpose is cognition. The second and third stages of the sophomore year - the perception stage, the main task is to combine the cultivation of aesthetics and guide students to establish ecological aesthetic ideals - this is the key to the ecological aesthetic education of art design, which is conducive to the cultivation of students' ecological sense of responsibility, and its purpose is to perceive; The main task of the three and four innovation stages is to cultivate students' ecological aesthetic creativity and lay a good foundation for the artistic dissemination of ecological aesthetics - this is the focus of ecological aesthetic education in art design, and is conducive to the final formation of students' ecological aesthetic thinking. The purpose is to innovate.

- Interaction

The course content of ecological aesthetic education starts from the perspective of ecological system, and integrates the idea of ecological aesthetic education into all the course content to form a systematic and interactive course content. The course content focuses on the relationship between man and nature, man and society, between man and man, and man and himself. The content of the whole course ranges from cultural history theory, cultural appreciation, aesthetic operation to the final comprehensive course, forming an interactive course system of recognizing beauty, knowing beauty and creating beauty. The value of art education and the knowledge between courses and courses have an inherent and inevitable connection. The task of ecological aesthetic education is to cultivate ecological aesthetic awareness and establish ecological aesthetic ideals, so as to guide the educated to live ecologically aesthetically. The goal of ecological aesthetic education for art students is to cultivate designers with ecological aesthetic concepts. The core task is to comply with the trend of aesthetic ecologicalization of art design. The ecological aesthetic education course cannot be independent of the professional learning of college students. It is necessary to extract aesthetic materials from professional learning to form a professional aesthetic section, and finally form an interdisciplinary and cross-border aesthetic education experience.

- Fusion

It points to a multi-integrated ecological aesthetic education curriculum evaluation system. The dimension of curriculum evaluation mainly includes three elements: the rationality of the curriculum, the degree of student development, and the performance status of teachers and students. Among them, the dimension of curriculum setting is to evaluate whether the curriculum setting is reasonable, which is mainly divided into three secondary dimensions: meeting the requirements of the training plan, meeting the actual needs of students and operability; the dimension of teacher-student performance status refers to the status of teachers and students in teaching activities. It is mainly divided into two dimensions: students' learning attitude and teachers' basic literacy. Student development is the main goal of curriculum design. The mission of ecological aesthetic education is to enhance students' aesthetic quality and humanistic quality, and at the same time, promote students' comprehensive and sustainable development, and ultimately realize the ideal of becoming an artist who lives in a poetic way. The evaluation of students' development level shows that the ecological aesthetic education course plays a role in promoting the development of students' ecological aesthetic quality.

- Development

Establish a curriculum guarantee system for ecological aesthetic education with diversified development. To be established from the following aspects. First, improve the school's ecological aesthetic education credit system and optimize the credit management methods. Establish a sound method for the credit recognition of elective courses, practical courses and activity courses for ecological aesthetic education, assign

instructors to college students participating in student associations and various art activities held by the school, and give corresponding grades and credits after assessment.

Second, cultivate ecologically conscious teachers. Teachers should not only have advanced teaching concepts, but also creativity and design passion. The teaching staff realizes inter-professional and interdisciplinary integration. Teachers should also establish the awareness of lifelong learning, and set up the value orientation of students' development as the goal and the attitude of tolerance towards others.

Third, students are required to extensively participate in extracurricular practice to enhance their innovative ability. Students should actively participate in various competitions to stimulate students' innovative consciousness and desire. Students should be actively organized to participate in social practice to promote the close integration of classroom teaching and extracurricular practice. Realize self-worth and enhance self-confidence and innovation.

Fourth, the characteristics of running a school show the style of ecological aesthetic education. Educator Suhomlinsky once said: "The purpose of running a school is to run a national spirit and a traditional culture." The integration of ecological aesthetic education and characteristic school-running is to seek a national spirit of respecting and loving nature, and to cultivate a traditional culture of "harmony between man and nature".

Fifth, family and social education help ecological aesthetic education. Ecological civilization is the main feature of future social civilization; ecological civilization literacy and ecological aesthetic literacy are important characteristics that people in modern society must have. The construction of ecological civilization and the improvement of people's ecological aesthetic quality are inseparable from the joint responsibility of society and family. Build an ecological aesthetic education "ecological body" that integrates school ecological aesthetic education, family ecological aesthetic education and social ecological aesthetic education, It is an inevitable development trend to promote ecological aesthetic education.

Sixth, the modern scientific and technological means to help the development of ecological aesthetic education. Use information and communication technology to connect the Internet with all walks of life including traditional industries, create a new ecology in new fields, and quickly sweep across all social fields. "The General Office of the State Council on Comprehensively Strengthening and Improving School Aesthetic Education" Work Opinions" also pointed out that it is necessary to "establish a network resource sharing platform for aesthetic education", relying on network resources for aesthetic education, encourage schools of all levels and types to develop the new situation of "Internet +", and strengthen the construction of mobile platforms between schools. Enrich the online courses of ecological aesthetic education in colleges and universities. Combined with the level of science and technology, smart phones enable mobile aesthetic methods and mobile aesthetic education to play a greater role in college aesthetic education courses under the important opportunities brought by Internet technology.

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